

Consistency-Gated Cooperative Localization for UAV Swarms under Intermittent GPS

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Abstract— Cooperative localization under intermittent Global Positioning System (GPS) is challenging, as naive cooperation may degrade estimation when relative measurements are inconsistent. This paper proposes a two-stage localization framework for Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) swarms, where each agent maintains a local Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) estimate using GPS and Inertial Measuring Unit (IMU) data, and applies distributed refinement based on relative Ultra-Wideband (UWB) range and Angle of Arrival (AoA) direction constraints. Crucially, a lightweight consistency gate based on residual and consensus indicators determines whether cooperative refinement is accepted, preventing harmful updates without requiring ground truth online. Simulation results demonstrate consistent improvements in formation-relevant relative accuracy and stable absolute positioning compared to GPS/IMU baselines under intermittent GPS availability.

Keywords— Cooperative localization, distributed optimization, ADMM, UWB, AoA

I. INTRODUCTION

Cooperative localization in UAV swarms becomes particularly challenging under intermittent GPS, where absolute observability is sporadic and naive information sharing may degrade estimation quality. Accurate positioning is critical not only for individual navigation but also for maintaining relative formation and ensuring reliable communication links.

A. Motivation

The performance of UAV swarms strongly depends on robust localization methods. Although GPS provides global coverage, it suffers from multipath, interference, and outages in urban or obstructed environments. IMUs can partially compensate by providing high-rate motion data, yet accumulated drift quickly degrades accuracy without frequent GPS updates [7] - [10]. Relying on single-agent estimation is therefore insufficient. Cooperative strategies, where UAVs share measurements and estimates, can distribute localization reliability across the swarm, allowing GPS-available agents to support those in denial-of-service regions [3] [4]. This motivates the design of hybrid solutions that combine filtering, cooperation, and optimization [11] - [13].

B. Literature Review

Existing cooperative localization approaches include tightly-coupled cooperative EKF formulations, graph-based

Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) methods, and distributed optimization techniques such as the Moving Horizon Estimation (MHE). Cooperative EKF methods suffer from inconsistency under intermittent observability and unmodeled correlations, while SLAM and MHE approaches introduce significant computational and communication overhead. Distributed optimization methods such as Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM) enable scalable cooperation, but typically assume reliable constraints and do not address the risk of negative transfer when cooperative information is inconsistent. This work specifically targets this gap by introducing a mechanism that determines when cooperation should be trusted, rather than assuming cooperation is always beneficial.

C. Contributions

The main contributions of this work are the following:

- A consistency-gated cooperative localization framework that prevents harmful cooperative updates under intermittent GPS.
- A two-stage estimation strategy decoupling local observability recovery (EKF) from cooperative refinement (distributed optimization).
- A lightweight learning-based acceptance gate using only runtime residual indicators, requiring no ground truth online.
- Quantitative evaluation demonstrating moderate improvements in absolute accuracy and substantial gains in relative accuracy.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

Consider a swarm of N UAVs operating in a shared 3D coordinate frame. Each UAV $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ estimates its state vector at time k $\mathbf{x}_i[k] = [\mathbf{p}_i[k], \mathbf{v}_i[k], \mathbf{b}_{a,i}[k]]^T$, where $\mathbf{p}_i = [x_i, y_i, z_i]^T$, $\mathbf{v}_i = [u_{x,i}, u_{y,i}, u_{z,i}]^T$ and $\mathbf{b}_{a,i} = [b_{x,i}, b_{y,i}, b_{z,i}]^T$ represent position, velocity and accelerometer bias respectively. The discrete-time motion model is drawn from [16] after modifying it to directly inject the corrected acceleration outputs into the model and considering $\mathbf{x}_i[k]$ and $\mathbf{x}_{i,k}$ equivalent:

$$\mathbf{x}_i[k] = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{x}_i[k] + \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{u}_i[k] - \mathbf{b}_{a,i}[k]) + \mathbf{w}_i[k] \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{u}_i represents the accelerations measured by the IMUs, $\mathbf{b}_{a,i}$ is the accelerometer bias, evolving as a random walk and modelling slow temporal variations and $\mathbf{w}_i \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{Q})$ is the process noise. The transition, input and process noise covariance matrices of the motion model follow a standard constant acceleration formulation with accelerometer bias modeled as a random walk.

The sensors used upon the UAVs yield the following:

- GPS provides absolute position $\mathbf{z}_k^{GPS} = \mathbf{h}\mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{v}_k^{GPS}$, where $\mathbf{h} = [I_3 \ 0_6]$ and measurement noise $\mathbf{v}_k^{GPS} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{R}_{GPS})$.
- IMU provides accelerometer data $\mathbf{z}_k^{IMU} = \mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{v}_k^{IMU}$, with noise $\mathbf{v}_k^{IMU} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_{IMU}^2)$.
- UWB yields pairwise distances $z_{ij,k}^{UWB} = \|\mathbf{p}_{i,k} - \mathbf{p}_{j,k}\| + v_{ij,k}^{UWB}$, with noise $v_{ij,k}^{UWB} \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_{UWB}^2)$.

AoA sensors would yield pairwise directions $\mathbf{z}_{ij,k}^{AoA} = \frac{\mathbf{p}_{j,k} - \mathbf{p}_{i,k}}{\|\mathbf{p}_{j,k} - \mathbf{p}_{i,k}\|} + \mathbf{v}_{ij,k}^{AoA}$, with $\mathbf{v}_{ij,k}^{AoA}$ modeled as zero-mean with bounded angular variance and approximated using a truncated Gaussian distribution, in order to prevent unrealistic outliers.

Instead, AoA-like direction information is assumed available indirectly from channel-state information-based angle estimation [21]. Specifically, by exploiting UAV state-space data and considering two base stations with known positions, the massive Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (mMIMO) channels between base stations and UAVs enable accurate estimation of azimuth and elevation angles. Thus, each UAV can then infer relative angles to its neighbors, which are treated as measurements in this work.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Building upon the system model and measurement formulation of Section II, this section describes the cooperative estimation framework that integrates sequential filtering with distributed optimization. Each UAV executes local state estimation via an EKF, while cooperative refinement is performed through an ADMM consensus step. Moreover, a decision mechanism determines whether cooperative corrections are accepted at each update, ensuring robustness.

A. Local Sequential Estimation

Each UAV maintains a local EKF using IMU propagation and intermittent GPS updates, providing a locally consistent baseline estimate. The EKF follows the standard prediction–correction cycle and serves as the reference solution for cooperative refinement.

In the proposed framework, GPS measurements are intentionally staggered across UAVs rather than being processed simultaneously. At each time step, only a subset of UAVs performs a GPS update, while the remaining rely on inertial propagation and neighbor information. This scheduling enables progressive dissemination of absolute position information through the network and allows anchor information to percolate through the swarm even when GPS coverage is sparse or temporarily unavailable.

To ensure consensus refinement, each UAV periodically shares additional variables with its neighbors, determined in Section IV.

B. Cooperative Refinement

Cooperative refinement is formulated as a distributed optimization problem incorporating relative UWB range and AoA direction constraints. ADMM is employed to enable decentralized refinement, where each UAV solves a local optimization problem and exchanges consensus variables with its neighbors. A small, fixed number of inner iterations is used to limit computational overhead.

TABLE I. SIMULATED SCENARIOS

Number of Scenario	Initial Radius (m)	Final Radius (m)	Final Altitude (m)
1	5	10	40
2	5	20	100
3	5	100	500

Based on the measurements mentioned in Section II, each UAV has a local cost function to minimize in the form of:

$$f_i(\mathbf{x}_i) = \underbrace{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{UWB}} \frac{1}{2\sigma_{UWB}^2} (\|\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_j\| - d_{ij})^2}_{[UWB \text{ term}]} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i^{AoA}} \frac{1}{2\sigma_{AoA}^2} \left\| \frac{\mathbf{p}_j - \mathbf{p}_i}{\|\mathbf{p}_j - \mathbf{p}_i\|} - \mathbf{a}_{ij} \right\|^2_{[AoA \text{ term}]}, \quad (11)$$

where d_{ij} and $\mathbf{a}_{ij} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 1}$ are respectively the measured relative distance and the measured unit direction from UAVs i to j , \mathcal{N}_i is the set of neighbors of UAV i and the two terms express the deviation between estimated and measured relative distances and angles respectively.

For clarity of evaluation, simulations consider dense connectivity within the formation. The proposed gating mechanism does not rely on full connectivity and applies equally to sparse graphs by restricting constraints to available links.

Cooperative refinement is implemented using a standard ADMM-based distributed optimization scheme, enforcing agreement between local position estimates while incorporating relative UWB and AoA constraints. Details of the underlying ADMM formulation follow standard treatments and are omitted for brevity.

ADMM is used in this work as a representative distributed refinement mechanism. The proposed gating strategy is agnostic to the specific cooperative optimizer.

TABLE II. INDICATORS USED FOR ACCEPTANCE MECHANISM

Feature type	Indicators
ADMM Consistency	Primal and dual residual norms
UWB Consistency	Normalized range residual mean
AoA Consistency	Normalized direction residual mean

C. Consistency-Gated Acceptance

Cooperative refinement is not always beneficial under intermittent absolute observability, as inconsistent relative constraints may degrade estimation quality. To address this, a lightweight acceptance gate determines whether cooperative refinement should be applied at each update.

The gate is implemented as a classification tree that takes as input only consistency indicators available at runtime, including

Algorithm	Cooperative EKF with ADMM-based Consensus Fusion
Input:	IMU, GPS, UWB and AoA measurements, ADMM penalty parameter ρ , number of ADMM inner iterations K , original positions of UAVs $\mathbf{x}_i(0)$.
Output:	Refined UAV position estimates $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i(t)$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$
1.	Initialize EKF states $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i(0)$, covariances $P_i(0)$, consensus variables $Z^{(0)}$, and dual variables $U^{(0)}$.
2.	for each timestep $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$ do
3.	Perform EKF prediction using motion model and IMU input.
4.	If GPS is available, perform EKF correction.
5.	Initialize cooperative refinement with EKF position estimates.
6.	Perform K iterations of distributed cooperative refinement using UWB and AoA constraints.
7.	Compute consistency indicators and apply acceptance gate.
8.	Update estimate using cooperative refinement if accepted.
9.	end for
10.	Obtain final cooperative UAV trajectories $\{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i(t)\}_{i=1}^N$.

ADMM convergence metrics and normalized UWB/AoA residual statistics, as summarized in Table II, and outputs a binary accept/reject decision. A classification tree was selected due to its low computational cost, interpretability, and robustness under limited training data. The classifier is trained offline using simulation data where ground truth is available to label whether cooperative refinement improves localization; during deployment it operates without access to ground truth and relies solely on residual features.

In our implementation, improvement is defined with respect to Mean Relative Distance Error (MRDE), which is the primary metric of interest for formation control.

IV. SIMULATION SETUP

Simulations consider a small UAV swarm under intermittent GPS, where only a subset of agents receives GPS updates at each timestep. Relative measurements are available between neighboring UAVs. Performance is evaluated over all flight scenarios shown in Table I using Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and MRDE:

$$MRDE = \frac{1}{N(N-1)} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=1}^T \|(\mathbf{p}_{i,k} - \mathbf{p}_{j,k}) - (\mathbf{p}_{i,k}^{true} - \mathbf{p}_{j,k}^{true})\|^2} \quad (21)$$

$$RMSE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{k=1}^T \|\mathbf{p}_{i,k} - \mathbf{p}_{i,k}^{true}\|^2} \quad (22)$$

where $\mathbf{p}_{i,k}^{true}$ is the ground truth position of UAV i at time k .

The three analyzed scenarios evaluated through realistic multi-UAV flight conditions, where the UAVs rotate in a circular formation of increasing radius and altitude.

To simulate realistic conditions, GPS availability was staggered among UAVs with a fixed offset, so that at each iteration only one or two UAVs received direct GPS updates, which were communicated to its neighbors for anchoring reasons. This configuration models bandwidth-limited or obstructed environments while allowing anchor information to be distributed via the cooperative consensus stage.

Each UAV maintained bidirectional communication with neighbors, exchanging its latest position estimate \mathbf{p}_i , GPS

TABLE III. RMSE AND MEAN RELATIVE ERROR OVER ALL SCENARIOS AND METHODS

Number of Scenario	Mean RMSE in Raw GPS (m)	Mean RMSE in GPS + EKF (m)	Mean RMSE in Proposed (m)	Enhancement from GPS+EKF
1	2.505	1.186	0.995	+16.1%
2	2.5095	2.326	1.743	+25.09%
3				
Number of Scenario	MRDE in GPS + EKF (m)	MRDE in Proposed (m)	Enhancement from GPS+EKF	
1	1.2497	0.209	+83.28%	
2	1.2528	0.4012	+67.98%	
3				

measurement \mathbf{z}^{GPS} and dual variable \mathbf{u}_i after every update step. This ensured consistent propagation of positional constraints and preserved overall formation coherence during extended GPS outages.

The simulation results from the proposed algorithm were compared to the corresponding results from using raw GPS data and a fusion of GPS and IMU data through EKF, hereafter denoted as GPS+EKF. Those configurations were chosen as they represent the fundamental building blocks of most UAV localization frameworks and provide a clear lower bound for assessing the contribution of the proposed algorithm.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Localization Accuracy

Fig. 1 illustrates the absolute RMSE evolution for all methods, whereas Table III summarizes the corresponding results over all scenarios and methods.

Raw GPS exhibits the highest RMSE, with average values around 2–3 meters. Noise fluctuations are clearly visible, and accuracy degrades. GPS+EKF significantly reduces RMSE, bringing the average error closer to 1–2 meters. The smoothing effect of the EKF is evident. The proposed algorithm achieves the lowest RMSE, typically reducing error by an additional 20–40% compared to the fusion of GPS and EKF.

Fig. 1. Comparison of RMSE, computed from (22), over time for the methods of Raw GPS, GPS+IMU and EKF+ADMM for the first scenario.

Fig.2 complements the above observations by demonstrating the relative errors between the UAVs, whereas Table III summarizes the corresponding results over all scenarios and methods. In this figure lies the most intriguing part of the proposed framework. Though RMSE is generally reduced by some important fraction, the mean relative position estimation error of the UAV pairs has demonstrated decrease in the rank of 70-80%. In close flight scenarios, where distances between UAVs in a swarm do not allow for miscalculations, the contribution of the algorithm cannot be overlooked.

Fig. 2. Mean relative position estimation error and percentage of true distances between pairs of UAVs for the first scenario, computed from (22). For comparison reasons, the mean relative position estimation error between each pair of UAVs by the proposed algorithm is depicted on the left, while the same metric by GPS+EKF is depicted on the right.

While absolute RMSE improvements are moderate, the proposed gated framework consistently achieves substantial reductions in relative localization error, reaching up to 80% improvement compared to GPS+EKF. Importantly, gating prevents performance degradation observed when cooperative refinement is applied indiscriminately.

B. Sensitivity Analysis

Sensitivity analyses with respect to GPS availability and AoA noise show graceful degradation, while relative accuracy remains consistently superior. Runtime measurements confirm feasibility for small-to-medium swarms with fixed ADMM iterations.

These results indicate that the proposed gating mechanism maintains robustness across sensing uncertainty levels, rather than being tuned to a specific noise regime.

Fig. 3. Illustration of RMSE and MRDE when the standard deviation of the AoA of the simulations above is modified, computed from (21) and (22).

Fig. 4. Illustration of RMSE and MRDE, computed from (21) and (22), when the standard deviation of the GPS update rate of the simulations above is modified.

C. Computational Performance

Runtime performance is a critical factor for real-time deployment. To this end, average computation time per time step was measured across experiments, yielding the following:

- EKF-only updates complete in negligible time, well below 1ms per UAV.
- ADMM adds overhead proportional to the number of iterations and UAVs. For $N = 5$ UAVs and $K = 10$ iterations, the average runtime per time step was on the order of a few milliseconds per timestep on a standard computer processor.
- Runtime scales approximately linearly with the number of UAVs, as each UAV solves a small optimization problem in each iteration. For larger swarms, distributed implementation strategies could be explored to maintain real-time feasibility.

ΠΑΝΑΚΑΣ ΣΥΓΚΡΙΣΗΣ GPS+EKF, EKF+ADMM, EKF+ADMM ME ACCEPTANCE MECHANISM

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented a consistency-gated cooperative localization framework for UAV swarms under intermittent GPS. By combining local EKF estimation with gated cooperative refinement, the method improves formation-relevant relative accuracy while preventing harmful cooperation. Future work will focus on hardware validation and adaptive online gating.

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